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The use of microfinance services among economically active disabled people – evidence from Uganda

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Abstract

This study investigates the use of microfinance services among economically active disabled people living in urban and semi-urban areas in Uganda. The findings suggest that economically active disabled people typically raise their starting capital from private savings or from family and friends. However, the study also illustrates that disabled people have easier access to microfinance services than previously assumed. A total of 89% of the survey's respondents state that they have used at least one type of microfinance services. Informal self-help schemes like ROSCAs are more easily accessed than are formal institutional schemes like MFIs, and disabled people access more savings than loans. The multivariate analysis shows that access to microfinance services is positively related to education level while negatively related to income from farming. Deaf people have generally less access to microfinance than other disability categories.

1. Introduction

According to the United Nations (UN 2008), approximately 10% of the global population has disabilities; 80% of these individuals live in developing countries, and for those who live on less than \$1 a day, 1 in 5 has a disability. The cost of disability is high for the affected individual, his/her family and for the society. All the same, disability is in general not an integrated part of development policies (Kett *et al.* 2009) and efforts to support disabled people tend to be based on charity and government support (Gooding & Marriot 2009) rather than socio-economic integration (ILO 2002; Lewis 2004). In developing countries, 80–90% of persons with disabilities do not have formal jobs and government and charity support are in practice limited, so most turn to self-employment (UN 2008).

For the self-employed access to capital is vital. It is argued that access to microfinance should be a priority in pro-disability livelihood policies (Handicap-International 2006; Cramm & Finkenflugel 2008; Martinelli & Mersland Forthcoming), but claims are put forth that disabled people seldom have access to microfinance (Cramm & Finkenflugel 2008). Data to

support the claim of low access are however limited and microfinance is mostly understood as microcredit. In this article, we broaden this view and we bring in first hand evidence to support the analysis. We concentrate the analysis on economically active disabled people and first analyse what were their initial source of capital to start out being self-employed. We then study whether economically active disabled people have access to credit, whether they are saving and to what degree they participate in informal financial arrangements like Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs). Finally, we search for individual characteristics that influence whether or not a disabled person has access to microfinance services.

A survey carried out by the National Union of Disabled People in Uganda (NUDIPU) makes up the data for this study. The survey covers 841 respondents that have participated in livelihood and microfinance trainings conducted by the NUDIPU. Only those disabled people who enjoyed at least a minimum level of existing economic activity were invited to the training. The findings indicate that economically active disabled people start out with their own means or with the help of families and friends. Even though the respondents are very poor (e.g., 53% reported a monthly income of less than 50 US dollars) they have much better access to microfinance than previously thought. A total of 89% of the survey's respondents state that they have used at least one type of microfinance services. There is evidence that women use microfinance services more than men, and married people appear to be more apt both to save and to borrow money than the unmarried. Farmers have less access to microfinance services than do people with income from other businesses. Deaf people appear to be worse off than other disabled people, particularly when it comes to accessing credit. From a policy perspective, finding a positive relation between education and the use of microfinance services is important.

The findings of this study illustrate the importance of understanding microfinance as a broader issue than that of the traditional credit provided by a Microfinance Institution (MFI) or a development project. A message of the study is the importance of getting disabled people to become economically active. This is what leads to integration into society and thereby

better access to services, in this case microfinance. The survey illustrates that the first “seeds” of economic activity in nearly all cases come from the disabled person himself/herself or from his/her immediate surroundings (families and friends) instead of from outside actors like donors or MFIs. Motivating those disabled people who do not engage in an economic activity to start saving would be a natural recommendation derived from this study.

The rest of this paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 discusses the disability market in Uganda and presents the microfinance services available. Section 3 reviews the disability literature related to microfinance and sets up the hypotheses to be tested. Section 4 presents the data and the methodologies. Section 5 presents and discusses the results. Section 6 concludes.

2. Microfinance services for disabled people

Defining disability is difficult, and depending on the definition used, researchers come up with percentages ranging from around 3% to nearly 20% of a given population. In Uganda, three surveys have studied the prevalence of disabilities. Using different definitions of disability, the Population and Housing Census (2002) reported that 3.5% of the population was made up of disabled people, the Uganda National Household Survey (2005) reported a figure of 7.1%, and the Uganda Demographic and Health Survey (2006) reported a figure of 20%. The question in the latter study was whether a person had difficulty seeing, hearing, walking or climbing stairs, remembering or concentrating, providing self-care, or communicating. The large differences in disability statistics are alarming but fall outside the scope of this paper. What is important is that regardless of statistical methods and definitions, the disability segment is large and should be at the forefront of development policies. At the same time, the disability segment constitutes an important market opportunity for providers of any goods or services, including microfinance.

Martinelli and Mersland (Forthcoming) explain that there are basically three schemes available for the supply of microfinance: formal institutional schemes, informal self-help schemes and ad-hoc schemes. *Institutional schemes* are formal organisations incorporated as

public banks, shareholder firms often registered as commercial banks or non-bank financial institutions, non-profit organisations often referred to as Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and formally registered member-based organisations like Savings and Credit Cooperatives (SACCOs). The term Microfinance Institution (MFI) is often used to identify the formal providers of microfinance.¹ Based on a limited set of data from a few MFI branches in Uganda, Mersland et al. (2009) provide evidence that only around 0.65% of the MFI clients have a disability, according to visible observations by the credit officers responsible for personal follow-up of the clients.

Informal self-help schemes are normally organised by the people themselves, without any support from an outside organisation. They are often referred to as Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs), have been around for centuries, and exist in virtually every developing country including Uganda (Bouman 1995). A group of 15-30 people pool their savings weekly or monthly. These savings are distributed as grants or loans amongst the members in a rotating system. Due to social stigma, it is argued, disabled people are often denied access to self-help microfinance schemes. In a study from Bangladesh, Thomas (2000) finds that the proportion of disabled members of groups varied from 0.3% to 5% in donor-supported self-help microfinance projects that did not specifically target disabled people, while the percentages of disabled members varied from 18% to 23.5% in projects specifically targeting disabled people but also allowing non-disabled members. To our knowledge, no prior study exists that considers the prevalence of disabled members in non-donor-initiated ROSCAs and to what degree disabled people participate in them. In this regard, our data introduce new knowledge.

Ad-hoc schemes are development projects or revolving funds organised especially for disabled people by NGOs, Community Based Organisations (CBOs) or Disabled People's Organisations (DPOs) and funded by donors (Handicap-International 2006). The focus of these schemes is to provide the beneficiaries with loans, and these loans are normally

¹ Some will not include SACCOs, public banks or commercial banks under the umbrella of the term MFI.

provided alongside other components like trainings or health services. High repayment rates are often not a major issue, and interest rates are normally subsidised. The sustainability of the services is typically low, and the number of beneficiaries reached in ad-hoc schemes is limited, often less than one-hundred (Handicap-International 2006). For those reached, ad-hoc schemes can be important. However, since the cost of ad-hoc schemes is disproportional high, the vast majority of disabled people can only be reached through self-help schemes or institutional schemes (Dyer 2003), which are the focus of this paper.

3. Literature review and hypotheses

The four questions guiding this study are as follows. 1) What is the original source of capital used by disabled people to start up economic self-employment activities? 2) To what extent do economically active disabled people access microfinance services? 3) What types of microfinance service are more easily accessed by disabled people? 4) What are the individual characteristics influencing whether or not a disabled person has access to microfinance services? Sub-section 3.1 discusses the three first questions while sub-section 3.2 focuses on the individual characteristics' possible influence on access to microfinance.

3.1 Initial source of working capital and access to microfinance services

It is commonly argued that disabled people are very poor and need access to external support from donors to form up the needed working capital to become self-employed. Over the years hundreds of projects, sponsored by organizations like the World Bank, Handicap International or Leonard Cheshire International, have provided disabled people with start-up capital to initiate self-employment activities. The results have been generally weak. The number of beneficiaries per project has been low and without the necessary personal aptitude, technical knowledge and market accessibility the initial working capitals have often faded. This should come as no surprise. The entrepreneurship literature (Carter & Auken 1990) is clear on the relation between personal economic sacrifice/risk and firm survival. The success rate for newly established businesses is positively related to the entrepreneurs' personal stakes in the projects. This knowledge is incorporated into most MFIs credit methodologies allowing

lending only to expand existing business activities (Ledgerwood 1999). When studying disabled people that are economically active we thus expect to find that existing activities have been initiated with their own means.

Mersland et al. (2009), building on Simanowitz (2001), explain that there are several mechanisms excluding disabled people from access to microfinance. These are exclusion by staff due to attitudes, exclusion by credit design, exclusion by non-disabled members in credit or savings groups, self-exclusion by the disabled themselves because of low self-esteem and repeated experiences of rejection during life, and exclusion because of the disability itself. Findings in Mersland et al. (2009), Handicap-International (2006) and Thomas (2000) confirm that few disabled people access credit in traditional MFIs or donor-supported self-help schemes. However, whether disabled people have access to commercial banks, SACCOs or ROSCAs is still unknown in the literature. Ex-ante expectations could indicate that since disabled people, like other poor people, are considered risk-averse, they should prefer regulated commercial banks when entrusting their savings because regulated banks are often considered the safest option when available. However, the business model of the commercial banks, which normally focus on better-off clients, could make it difficult for most disabled people to access their services. Whether disabled people will access commercial banks is thus uncertain. At least in theory, the SACCOs have a business model more aligned with the members' needs (Mersland 2009) and should therefore be relatively more able to reach out to disabled people. As for the ROSCAs, local stigma regarding disabled people could indicate that they are excluded from membership or may experience inappropriate pressure from other group members (Montgomery 1996). However, since those living close to the disabled people are the ones with the best opportunity to assess their economic activities, membership in ROSCAs is probably the most commonly used microfinance service for disabled people, as it is generally for poor people in most developing countries (Bouman 1995).

When it comes to the type of service accessed, we expect to find that disabled people access savings to a much larger extent than they access loans. This would be in line with any study

researching the money management practices of poor people (Rutherford 2000; Matin *et al.* 2002). Poor people prefer saving, and they save to a much larger extent than non-poor people tend to believe they do (Christen *et al.* 2004). Poor people save because they must. Huge fluctuation in incomes makes it impossible for most poor people not to save at least during some parts of the year (Rutherford 2000). We thus expect to find that a considerable share of the respondents indicate that they save money.

3.2 Microfinance services and individual characteristics

The influence of a large number of individual characteristics on disabled people's access to microfinance is examined in this study. As for personal characteristics, we investigate differences along four dimensions: age, gender, marital status and number of dependants. Generally, young and old people have lesser access to microfinance than do the middle-aged (Helms 2006). Disabled women tend to be worse-off than disabled men (UN 2008). In microfinance, however, women generally tend to be more frequent users of services than men (Aghion & Morduch 2005). An ex-ante expectation is therefore uncertain, but since we study economic active disabled people we hypothesize disabled women to have greater access than disabled men. The proposed increased stability for married people makes it generally easier for them to access microfinance than it is for the unmarried and the widowed. In addition, it may be reasonable to expect that those with more dependants are poorer and less credit-worthy than families with fewer mouths to feed.

Our study includes two disability-related characteristics: the type of disability and the age when the respondents became disabled. Three groups of disabilities are investigated: physical handicaps, blindness and deafness. Within the disability community, it is argued that the blind and the deaf are worse off than those with physical handicaps, and hence, that they do not access microfinance services as easily (Handicap-International 2006). As for the age at which the respondents acquired their disabilities, a possible expectation may be that persons are less able to cope with the disability if their handicaps emerge when the individuals in question are

younger, since they then may have poorly developed social skills and may have been denied education (Handicap-International 2006).

The last set of variables includes education level as well as the main and secondary sources of income. Generally, microfinance is accessed by “medium poor” with some form of assets and education (Helms 2006). We thus expect that access to microfinance services is positively related to the level of education. Specifically, we expect that the higher the level of education, the more likely it is that disabled people will save or borrow money. Prior studies (Helms 2006) find that people are more involved in microfinance if they have income from other sources of business than farming. We expect that this conclusion will hold among disabled persons as well. All our hypotheses are summarised in Table 1.

[Insert Table 1 about here]

4. Data and methodology

Uganda has a relatively well-developed microfinance industry with presence in most urban and semi-urban areas.² The data for this study are collected by the National Union of Disabled Persons of Uganda (NUDIPU) in trainings organised for economically active disabled people. The trainings take place in urban centres and those participating are in general urban and semi-urban dwellers. With the help of local NUDIPU members and district officials responsible for disability rehabilitation, all disabled persons with some kind of economic self-employment activity were invited to participate in the training. Mobilising participants for the trainings has been easy according to the NUDIPU, indicating that disabled people, if they have working capacity, are often involved in some economic activity. During the trainings, which took place in 2008, a questionnaire forming the dataset used in this study was distributed. When needed, a NUDIPU official helped the participants to complete the questionnaires. Generally, according to NUDIPU, around 80% of the participants filled out

² For more information about the Ugandan microfinance sector, consult the web-page of the Association of Micro Finance Institutions of Uganda (AMFIU), www.amfiu.org.ug

the questionnaires.³ Taken as a whole, the dataset represents disabled persons with existing economic activities living in urban or semi-urban areas. In total, the dataset consists of 841 respondents.

The specific variables used in this study are described in Table 2. Except for the respondents' number of dependants, all variables are indicator variables. These variables are equal to one if the respondent belongs to a certain sub-category and zero otherwise. Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for each of the variables. Panel A shows that a majority of the respondents are middle-aged but that both old and young people are represented in the study. There are slightly more men than women participating in the survey. Two-thirds of the respondents are married. Twelve percent of the respondents are deaf and 13% are blind, and the rest (76%) have other types of physical handicaps. People with mental handicaps were not excluded, but in practice, none of these participated in the training. The majority of the respondents got their disability either at birth or during their childhood. One out of ten respondents has no education whatsoever. Forty-four percent have completed primary school, while 47% have attained an education level higher than that of primary school. Half of the participants achieve their primary income from farming and an additional 39% have it as their secondary source of income.

[Insert Table 2 about here]

Panel B of Table 3 describes the sample further. The respondents are generally very poor, with monthly income below 100,000 Ugandan shillings (about 50 USD) for more than half of the sample. This is also reflected in the sizes of the participants' ROSCA contributions, savings accounts and loans. For those who are members of a ROSCA group, the monthly contributions are small. Moreover, the current balance for people who save is also very low. The size of the loans appears to be slightly larger. Panel B of Table 3 also includes the respondents' own assessment of the seriousness of their disability. The respondents are asked

³ The questionnaire is available from the authors upon request.

to what degree their disability affects their work. Most people answered “medium”, while few considered their handicap to either have a very small or a very large effect on their ability to carry out their work.

[Insert Table 3 about here]

5. Findings and discussion

Figure 1 shows that most disabled people that are economically active got their starting capital from their own means (personal savings or sale of assets) or from family members. In particular, note that loans are generally not what are used to start up businesses. This confirms our hypothesis that disabled people are not different from non-disabled people when it comes to financing the initiation of their economic activities. The findings also prove, in contrast to what many DPOs and disability advocates claim, that many disabled people do not need donor interventions to get involved in business ventures.

[Insert Figure 1 about here]

Now, sub-section 5.1 investigates how extensive the use of microfinance services is among economically active disabled people. The analyses are conducted on a large number of sub-samples based on individual characteristics. Sub-section 5.2 applies all of the individual characteristics using a multivariate logit analysis.

5.1 Microfinance and individual characteristics

To what extent do economically active disabled people have access to microfinance services? Table 4 presents the findings. A total of 558 out of the 841 respondents (66%) state that they are members of a ROSCA.⁴ Seventy-two percent of the respondents save money regularly,

⁴ The percentage share is estimated relative to the total sample of 841 respondents. Respondents who have not answered the question are assumed not to use the microfinance service in question. The number of missing observations is low, and robustness checks indicate that no conclusion is altered if the percentages are computed from the number of respondents who have actually answered the question.

and 50% (70% of all the people who save regularly) save to an account in a formal institution, defined as a commercial bank, MFI or SACCO. Thirty-nine percent of the respondents have borrowed money, but only 15% had a loan at the time the survey was conducted. Untabulated results show that 748 persons, 89% of the respondents, have borrowed, saved or been members of a ROSCA. Even if the respondents who have only participated in a ROSCA are excluded, 80% of the respondents have been involved in microfinance services. Taken together, a surprisingly high share of economically active disabled people do access different forms of microfinance services. The findings that more people access savings than loans and more participate in ROSCAs than in MFIs are however not surprising as they confirm general microfinance knowledge (Rutherford 2000).

[Insert Table 4 about here]

The fact that only about 40% of those who report having had a loan currently have an outstanding loan is interesting. Since the microfinance market in Uganda has grown steadily the reason cannot be that supply of credit has been reduced. We believe that the reason is to be found in the MFI-customer relationship. For instance, disabled people may have defaulted on their loans and thus have been denied renewals, or they may have found partnering with the MFI to be too expensive due to high interest rates or too troublesome due to the nature of their disabilities (for instance, the weekly group meetings demanded by some MFIs can be costly and time-consuming for a person in need of a personal assistant in order to attend a meeting). Another plausible explanation is that the MFI has found servicing the disabled person to be too difficult. For example, communicating with a deaf person can be challenging and time-consuming. However, the finding that 66% are members of a ROSCA illustrates that the ongoing servicing of disabled people should not be impossible. We thus recommend that new research looks into loan-renewals and MFI-customer dynamics concerning microfinance and disabled people.

Are there individual characteristics that influence whether or not a disabled person has access to microfinance services? We begin analysing this question by investigating differences between sub-groups in Table 4. Our first hypothesis regarding individual characteristics says that middle-aged people have easier access to microfinance services than do young and old people. Panel A of Table 4 suggests that teenagers definitely have lesser access than others to such services. Still, it does not appear that the oldest group of people is particularly worse off when it comes to savings or ROSCA participation. Regarding borrowing, our findings appear to be in line with the hypothesis. The age group from 36 to 50 years has a considerably higher proportion of loans than the other groups. Our second hypothesis says that women are more frequent users of microfinance services than men are. There is a significant difference in favour of women when ROSCA is considered.⁵ However, when saving and borrowing are evaluated, the differences are small and insignificant. In fact, males appear to be saving slightly more than females. The third hypothesis is that married people are more involved in microfinance than the unmarried are. Table 4 confirms this expectation.

Panel B of Table 4 shows how access to microfinance services is related to disability characteristics. We hypothesise that it is easier for people with a physical handicap to access microfinance services than it is for the blind and deaf. This hypothesis is only partly confirmed in this first analysis. As for membership in ROSCAs, deaf people have significantly less access to this service than do people with a physical handicap. However, there is no significant difference between people with a physical handicap and the blind. When it comes to savings, both the blind and the deaf appear to be worse off. Nevertheless, deaf people seem to have a relatively higher share of their savings in formal institutions. Contrary to our expectations, there is no significant difference between the groups when access to microcredit is considered. Still, when the groups are asked about their current situation, it emerges that far more physically disabled people have a loan than do blind and

⁵ We apply the term "significant" when the statistical significance level is below 10% in a two-sided t-test. The t-tests are available from the authors upon request.

deaf people. This should again motivate researchers to look into MFI-customer dynamics. Why do not blind and deaf people continue borrowing?

The findings support the hypothesis that a person being disabled since birth or childhood is the one with less access to microfinance. People who have been disabled since birth are less frequently members of a ROSCA and are also less involved in savings. The respondents who became handicapped as teenagers and adults have also had more loans than the rest.

Panel C of Table 4 outlines differences between sub-groups when education and source of income are considered. We expect that access to microfinance services is positively related to education. This hypothesis is generally confirmed. People without any education are less likely to be members of ROSCAs. The sub-groups appear to be relatively equally involved in saving, but there are huge differences when the type of saving is considered. People with a higher education level typically save in formal institutions, while only half of the no-education, regular-saving group does the same. There are significant differences between all sub-groups, suggesting that formal saving is an increasing function of the level of education. The same picture is found when access to microcredit is considered. People with a higher education level borrow more money than do people with only primary education, who again borrow more than people without any education. The last part of Panel C reports differences in microfinance involvement based on main and secondary sources of income. We expect that people with income from other businesses than farming will be more frequent users of microfinance services than farmers. We find some support for the hypothesis, but only when loans are considered. Income from farming seems thus not to restrict access to other types of microfinance services.

5.2 Multivariate analysis

This sub-section presents the results of a multivariate logit regression where all individual characteristics are controlled for simultaneously. Each of the dependent variables listed in

Table 2 is regressed on the explanatory variables for individual characteristics. The results from the five regressions are displayed in Table 5.

[Insert Table 5 about here]

The first regression (column one) has ROSCA membership as the dependent variable. The first set of explanatory variables is age. Age2 (20-35 years) is excluded from the analysis, so the coefficients on the other age-groups are to be interpreted relative to this group. We note that teenagers appear to be significantly less likely to join a ROSCA than are the others. The data do not support any significant differences between the other age-groups. The coefficient on gender is negative and significant, suggesting that women are more frequently members of ROSCAs than are men. The disability category does not seem to matter for participation in ROSCAs, but people who encountered their disability at birth are less likely to be part of a ROSCA. We obtain clear and significant results when education level is considered. The data show that those without education are less likely to be members of a ROSCA than are people with primary-level education and higher.

The two next regressions relate to saving. The first one studies saving in general, while the other analyses saving in formal institutions. The results are quite similar, meaning that the individual characteristics that drive saving in general are also the driving forces for saving in formal institutions. The results show no significant differences related to age and gender, but they do indicate that married people tend to be more involved in saving than unmarried people. Deaf and blind people tend to save less than physically disabled people. Consistent with this result, we also find that the blind save less in formal institutions. An interesting result is the one showing that even if deaf people in general are less prone to save than those with a physical handicap, they tend to save more in formal institutions. This means that deaf people put a much higher share of their savings in formal institutions than do the two other disability groups. We do not find this surprising. Since saving in a ROSCA or similar requires considerable communication with other members, deaf people prefer putting their savings into

formal institutions where they do not have to engage much in communication. Regarding the age of emergence of the disability, people who became disabled as adults seem to save more than others do. Saving also appears to be positively related to education level. However, the coefficients are significant only for the persons whose education level is above that of primary school.

The two final regressions analyse borrowing probability as a function of individual characteristics. The first one investigates whether the respondents have ever borrowed, whereas the second one focuses on those who are currently (i.e., at the time the survey was conducted) borrowing. The first regression suggests that the middle-aged are more likely to borrow than the three other sub-groups, a finding in accordance with our hypothesis. Moreover, both regressions strongly indicate that females have better access to microcredit than do males. Married people also seem better off as far as access to loans is considered. Deaf people are less likely to have loans today than are the blind and physically disabled. Surprisingly, there is some evidence that people who have been disabled since birth are currently more prone to borrow than others. In accordance with our hypotheses, people with an education level above that of primary school borrow significantly more than the rest, while farmers seem to be worse off than others as far as access to microcredit is concerned.

Overall, the findings from the multivariate analysis support our hypotheses.⁶ There is clear evidence that women borrow more and more frequently participate in ROSCAs than do men. There is some evidence that the middle-aged have better access to microfinance services than others, particularly teenagers. Married people are more likely to both save and borrow money than are the unmarried. There is also evidence that deaf people are worse off with regard to saving and access to microcredit. Persons with a higher education level than that of primary school have better access to microfinance services than those with no education. This conclusion is robust, as all regressions report identical findings. The regressions show that

⁶ A relatively large number of respondents did not indicate a secondary source of income. This depresses the number of observations in the multivariate regressions. However, none of the conclusions are altered if the secondary source of income is excluded from the analysis.

farmers appear to be less involved in microfinance than others are, but the coefficient is only significant as far as borrowing is concerned.

6. Conclusion

Using new data from a survey carried out by the National Union of Disabled People in Uganda (NUDIPU) this paper responds to the need for empirical evidence in the study of microfinance access for disabled people (Martinelli & Mersland Forthcoming). The findings indicate that even though the respondents are very poor (e.g., 53% reported a monthly income of less than 50 US dollars) they are indeed involved in economic activities and make more use of microfinance services than previously thought. Seventy-two percent report that they save regularly (50% in a formal institution) and 39% have borrowed money. Sixty-six percent are members of informal financial groups like ROSCAs. When it comes to the personal characteristics of those accessing microfinance, the findings generally echo existing microfinance knowledge. For instance, women have better access than men, married people are more prone to both save and borrow money than are the unmarried, and farmers have less access to microfinance services, especially loans, than do people with income from other businesses. Regarding disability characteristics, the findings confirm the expectation that deaf people are more excluded than are other disabled people, particularly when it comes to accessing credit.

From a policy perspective, the paper presents several interesting findings. For instance, the positive relation between education and the use of microfinance services highlights the importance of assuring education for disabled children. Another message of this study is the importance of getting disabled people to become economically active. As illustrated, disabled people with some kind of economic activity are integrated into society and thereby have access to services—in this case, microfinance. However, the survey suggests that the first “seeds” of economic activity should come from the disabled person himself/herself or from his/her immediate surroundings (families and friends) instead of from outside actors like

donors or MFIs. Motivating those disabled people who do not engage in an economic activity to start saving would thus be a natural recommendation derived from this study.

The little available knowledge and literature on microfinance and disability should motivate more research. There is a particular need to study disabled people's involvement in microfinance as compared to that of non-disabled people. Likewise, studies are needed to assess microfinance use by disabled people living in rural areas. Similarly, there is a need to study the dynamics of the disabled customer-MFI relationship and what factors enable or disenable disabled people's access to microfinance. Finally, we recommend studying how access to microfinance influences disabled people's quality of life and compare groups with and without access to services. In particular, such studies should not only look at possible improvement in incomes and assets but should also study whether access to microfinance influences disabled people's self esteem and general integration into society.

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Table 1: Summary of Hypotheses

	Hypothesis
<i>Source of Capital</i>	Economically active disabled people have financed the initiation of their income generating activities with their own means.
<i>Microfinance Services</i>	Informal self-help schemes are more easily accessed by disabled people than formal institutional schemes. Disabled people access more savings than loans.
<i>Characteristics</i>	
Age	Middle-aged people have easier access to microfinance services than do young and old people.
Gender	Women are more frequent users of microfinance services than are men.
Marital Status	Married people are more involved in microfinance than are unmarried people.
Number of Dependants	Access to microfinance services is negatively related to number of dependants.
Type of disability	It is easier for people with a physical handicap than for the blind and deaf to access microfinance services.
Age of disability.	People use more microfinance services if they were older when they became handicapped.
Education	There is a positive relationship between the education level and the use of microfinance services.
Type of Business	People with income from farming are less likely to be involved in microfinance than are people with income from other businesses.

Table description: Table 1 displays the study's hypotheses for the empirical analyses.

Table 2: Variable Definitions

Dependent Variables	Definitions
ROSCA	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is part of a ROSCA-group, 0 otherwise.
Regular Savings	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent saves regularly, 0 otherwise.
Savings in Formal Inst.	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent keeps his/her savings in a formal institution such as a commercial bank, MFI or SACCO; 0 if savings are outside of a financial institution or in a ROSCA-group.
Loan Ever	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has ever had a loan, 0 otherwise.
Loan Today	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent had a loan in 2008, 0 otherwise.
Independent Variables	Definitions
Age1(Teenagers)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is a teenager, 0 otherwise.
Age2(20-35 Years)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is 20-35 years old, 0 otherwise.
Age3(36-50 Years)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is 36-50 years old, 0 otherwise.
Age4(Over 50 Years)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is above 50 years old, 0 otherwise.
Gender (Male=1)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is male, 0 if female.
Marital Status (Married=1)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is married, 0 otherwise.
Dependants	The respondent's number of dependants.
Disability Category1(Physical)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has a physical handicap, 0 otherwise.
Disability Category2(Deaf)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is deaf, 0 otherwise.
Disability Category3(Blind)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent is blind, 0 otherwise.
Age Disability1(Birth)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent was born with his/her handicap, 0 otherwise.
Age Disability2(Childhood)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent got his/her handicap during childhood, 0 otherwise.
Age Disability3(Teenage)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent got his/her handicap as a teenager, 0 otherwise.
Age Disability4(Adult)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent got his/her handicap as an adult, 0 otherwise.
Education Level1(None)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent does not have any education, 0 otherwise.
Education Level2(Primary)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has completed primary school, 0 otherwise.
Education Level3(Above Primary)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has education above primary school level, 0 otherwise.
Main Source of Income (Farming=1)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has farming as his/her main source of income, 0 otherwise.
Secondary Source of Income (Farming=1)	Indicator variable equal to 1 if the respondent has farming as his/her secondary source of income, 0 otherwise.

Table description: Table 2 lists and defines the variables used in the empirical analyses of this study.

Figure description: Figure 1 illustrates the source of starting capital for 794 of the 841 respondents of the survey. 47 respondents did not state the source of their starting capital.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Total Sample 841

Panel A: Variables Applied in the Multivariate Analysis

Personal Characteristics		Disability Characteristics		Education and Income	
<u>Age</u>		<u>Type of Disability</u>		<u>Education</u>	
Teenagers	4 %	Physical	76 %	None	9 %
20-35 years	41 %	Deaf	12 %	Primary	44 %
36-50 years	34 %	Blind	13 %	Above Primary	47 %
Over 50 years	20 %	<u>Age Disability</u>		<u>Main Source of Income</u>	
<u>Gender</u>		Birth	19 %	Farming	50 %
Male	59 %	Childhood	50 %	Not Farming	50 %
Female	41 %	Teenage	13 %	<u>Secondary Source of Income</u>	
<u>Marital Status</u>		Adult	19 %	Farming	39 %
Married	66 %			Not Farming	61 %
Not Married	34 %				

Panel B: Further Descriptive Statistics

<u>Monthly Income</u>		<u>Balance of Savings Account</u>		<u>Disability Effect</u>	
Above 1,000,000	8 %	Above 1,000,000	5 %	None	5 %
700,000 - 1,000,000	5 %	700,000 - 1,000,000	3 %	Low	17 %
400,000 - 700,000	8 %	400,000 - 700,000	8 %	Medium	53 %
100,000 - 400,000	25 %	100,000 - 400,000	29 %	High	18 %
Less than 100,000	53 %	Less than 100,000	54 %	Very High	7 %
<u>Monthly Contribution ROSCA</u>		<u>Size of Last Loan</u>			
Above 50,000	9 %	Above 1,000,000	11 %		
25,000 - 50,000	16 %	700,000 - 1,000,000	10 %		
10,000 - 25,000	22 %	400,000 - 700,000	17 %		
Less than 10,000	54 %	100,000 - 400,000	45 %		
		Less than 100,000	17 %		

Table description: Table 3 lists percentage shares of respondents in various sub-samples based on individual characteristics.

Table 4: Who do Microfinance?

Panel A: Personal Characteristics

	Total Sample:	Age:				Gender:		Marital Status	
		<u>Teenagers</u>	<u>20-35 years</u>	<u>36-50 years</u>	<u>Over 50 years</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Female</u>	<u>Married</u>	<u>Not Married</u>
ROSCA	66 %	30 %	65 %	74 %	64 %	63 %	71 %	69 %	63 %
Regular Savings	72 %	55 %	72 %	74 %	69 %	72 %	71 %	75 %	65 %
Savings in Formal Inst.	50 %	39 %	52 %	53 %	45 %	52 %	48 %	55 %	41 %
Loan Ever	39 %	21 %	35 %	48 %	37 %	38 %	41 %	44 %	30 %
Loan Today	15 %	6 %	15 %	18 %	13 %	13 %	19 %	17 %	12 %

Panel B: Disability Characteristics

	Total Sample:	Type of Disability:			Age Disability:			
		<u>Physical</u>	<u>Deaf</u>	<u>Blind</u>	<u>Birth</u>	<u>Childhood</u>	<u>Teenage</u>	<u>Adult</u>
ROSCA	66 %	69 %	50 %	67 %	54 %	69 %	73 %	68 %
Regular Savings	72 %	76 %	58 %	64 %	68 %	72 %	74 %	77 %
Savings in Formal Inst.	50 %	54 %	48 %	37 %	46 %	53 %	51 %	49 %
Loan Ever	39 %	41 %	37 %	38 %	37 %	38 %	45 %	41 %
Loan Today	15 %	18 %	7 %	11 %	16 %	17 %	13 %	12 %

Panel C: Education and Income

	Total Sample:	Education Level:			Main Source of Income:		Secondary Source of Income:	
		<u>None</u>	<u>Primary</u>	<u>Above Primary</u>	<u>Farming</u>	<u>Not Farming</u>	<u>Farming</u>	<u>Not Farming</u>
ROSCA	66 %	52 %	67 %	69 %	67 %	68 %	65 %	71 %
Regular Savings	72 %	65 %	70 %	75 %	72 %	73 %	73 %	71 %
Savings in Formal Inst.	50 %	32 %	41 %	63 %	47 %	56 %	53 %	50 %
Loan Ever	39 %	20 %	38 %	45 %	33 %	46 %	39 %	44 %
Loan Today	15 %	4 %	13 %	19 %	13 %	18 %	17 %	18 %

Table description: Table 4 displays the proportions of disabled persons who have access to microfinance services, compared with the dependant variables in Table 2. The sub-groups are constructed based on the independent variables in Table 2.

Table 5: Multivariate Analysis

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable:									
	ROSCA (Yes=1)		Savings (Yes=1)		Type of Savings (Formal Inst.=1)		Loan Ever (Yes=1)		Loan Today (Yes=1)	
	Coefficient	z-value	Coefficient	z-value	Coefficient	z-value	Coefficient	z-value	Coefficient	z-value
Age1(Teenagers)	-1.68	-2.72	-0.88	-1.45	0.18	0.27	-0.99	-1.45	-0.24	-0.30
Age3(36-50 Years)	0.17	0.67	0.07	0.27	0.04	0.18	0.39	1.76	0.35	1.27
Age4(Over 50 Years)	-0.27	-0.88	-0.45	-1.51	-0.19	-0.62	0.19	0.67	0.03	0.08
Gender (Male=1)	-0.55	-2.37	0.00	-0.02	-0.11	-0.50	-0.41	-1.99	-0.70	-2.79
Marital Status (Married=1)	0.29	1.15	0.39	1.66	0.66	2.85	0.51	2.24	0.41	1.43
Dependants	-0.14	-0.98	-0.20	-1.42	0.05	0.39	0.02	0.12	0.04	0.23
Disability Category2(Deaf)	-0.40	-1.15	-0.72	-2.35	0.66	1.90	0.19	0.59	-1.04	-1.89
Disability Category3(Blind)	0.18	0.51	-0.75	-2.39	-0.61	-1.90	0.15	0.48	-0.03	-0.08
Age Disability2(Childhood)	0.37	1.32	0.06	0.20	0.22	0.80	-0.09	-0.36	-0.45	-1.46
Age Disability3(Teenage)	0.82	2.06	0.35	0.94	-0.06	-0.17	0.17	0.50	-0.74	-1.67
Age Disability4(Adult)	0.59	1.59	0.73	1.99	0.44	1.28	0.37	1.13	-0.55	-1.37
Education Level2(Primary)	0.68	1.79	0.53	1.50	0.47	1.18	0.42	1.08	0.87	1.34
Education Level3(Above Primary)	0.70	1.80	0.61	1.67	1.52	3.75	0.94	2.36	1.49	2.29
Main Source of Income (Farming=1)	-0.20	-0.79	0.00	-0.02	-0.28	-1.20	-0.68	-3.02	-0.31	-1.14
Secondary Source of Income (Farming=1)	-0.30	-1.22	0.33	1.38	0.04	0.15	-0.62	-2.76	-0.22	-0.81
Intercept	0.74	1.46	0.59	1.28	-1.15	-2.28	-0.59	-1.21	-1.95	-2.67
	<i>n</i>	505	<i>n</i>	533	<i>n</i>	478	<i>n</i>	500	<i>n</i>	500
	<i>Pseudo R</i> ²	5.12 %	<i>Pseudo R</i> ²	4.68 %	<i>Pseudo R</i> ²	8.49 %	<i>Pseudo R</i> ²	5.39 %	<i>Pseudo R</i> ²	6.41 %

Table description: Table 5 shows results from a logit regression analysis of each of the dependent variables in Table 2 on all explanatory variables. For each individual characteristic, one indicator variable is dropped to avoid perfect multicollinearity. Each regression coefficient is to be interpreted relative to the excluded indicator variable. Regression coefficients, z-values, number of observations (*n*) and explanatory power (*Pseudo R*²) are displayed for all regressions.